
***Bacillus coagulans* as target microorganism in the sterilization of double and triple-concentrated tomato paste**

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ABSTRACT

Bacillus coagulans has been used as the reference microorganism in the sterilization of double and triple-concentrated aseptically produced tomato paste, despite the absence of a target or criterion in the sterilization of such high-acid food products. In the present review, to validate the choice of *B. coagulans* as the target microorganism in this process, the thermal resistance parameters of the microorganisms associated with the spoilage of tomato products were compiled. The D- and z-values were used to calculate the sterilization temperatures necessary to achieve 7, 6, and 5 logarithmic reductions of the potential microbial population in a standard aseptic processing system used in the tomato industry. This process is known to cause color degradation, with an increase in the rate of nonenzymatic browning of tomato paste. The calculated values were compared and the results from industrial production were evaluated to ascertain that using *B. coagulans* as the target microorganism in the sterilization of aseptically processed tomato paste will ensure microbiological stability and compliance with the legal requirements related to foodborne pathogens while allowing to minimize the effects of this thermal process on the quality of tomato paste as well as improve heat-economy, which is critical in an industrial process where energy costs account for a significant portion of total expenses.

Keywords: thermal treatment, aseptic processing, sterilization, tomato paste, food spoilage.

INTRODUCTION

Tomato is both an important source of nutrition and vitamins, and a starting material for the food processing industry. Tomatoes can be used to make a variety of goods, such as tomato juice, tomato paste, diced/peeled tomatoes, strained tomato pulp, sauces, and powder. Tomato paste is perhaps the most essential product for the industrial market because it is used as a base for a wide range of other food products (1).

Around 1900, industrial processing of tomatoes

into pastes, pulps, and other products began in Italy, Portugal, Spain, and the United States. Since then the tomato processing business has grown globally.

Food safety has become increasingly more important and the quality and microbiological safety of processed tomato paste are essential requirements for commercial success.

Tomato processing in the Mediterranean area is seasonal, lasting about 50–70 days each year. Tomatoes come in a multitude of varieties and

their quality is greatly influenced by weather conditions. This means that the tomatoes must be processed quickly and efficiently, and special consideration must be given to microbiological hazards.

The following forms of microbial deterioration can be seen in processed tomato products: (a) tomato spoilage, i.e. bacterial and fungi growth before processing; (b) inadequate heat processing; (c) contamination after processing, e.g. during packaging; and (d) development of thermophilic bacteria in the stored product (2).

Tomato spoilage with fungi is also becoming more relevant, considering they may produce a wide range of secondary metabolites (mycotoxins) which are of concern as potentially dangerous food contaminants that can remain in the final product.

After the introduction of juice evaporators for the manufacture of concentrated orange and tomato juice in the 1950s, colonization of the evaporators and process lines by lactic acid bacteria (LAB) resulted in concentrates with off-flavors and other quality issues (3). There were additional cases where technology developments have resulted in microbiological concerns. Industry recognized that heat resistant molds (HRM) could grow in shelf-stable fruit juices and had to be regulated by suitable processing, packaging, sanitation and ingredient supply, as a result of these technologies (4).

The intrinsic characteristics of processed tomato concentrate (pH below 4.5, with high content of organic acids and sugars) are a challenge for the survival and growth of most bacteria, so the most relevant foodborne microorganisms, in what concerns microbiological

stability of this product, are mostly acid lactic bacteria, some heat resistant molds, and thermo-acidophilic spore-formers.

Quality parameters of processed tomato concentrate may be considerably affected by thermal treatments during processing, hence adequate consideration must be given to its design. With the advent of aseptic processing in the tomato industry sterilization became the standard method for killing or inactivating pathogenic microorganisms, and the most resistant spoilage bacteria and its spores. Sterilization is more aggressive than pasteurization, meaning more organoleptic alterations may occur in the final product (5).

Microbiological stability of aseptic tomato concentrate implies that sterility of the source product is retained during the aseptic filling and throughout the period of storage and its use.

Concerning processed tomato concentrate, *Clostridium botulinum* is not usually considered a problem when designing a thermal process to make a shelf-stable product, because it is accepted that the spores of this microbe will not thrive or generate toxins at pH value lower than 4.5 (6). Nevertheless, *C. botulinum* growth and toxin production have been observed at pH levels lower than 4.5. The researchers attributed the unexpected growth and toxin production in these cases to local pH changes in non-homogeneous conditions and *C. botulinum* growth before pH equilibrium, or to the fact that fungi establish microenvironments, with a pH value above 4.5, within or adjacent to the mycelial mat (7–9). If the pH is higher than 4.5, then it is possible for *C. botulinum* to grow and, therefore, toxin formation is likely (10).

Acid fruit juices were processed for years using “Hot-Fill-Hold” pasteurization processes. The most likely spoilage flora considered then were yeasts like *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, heat-resistant molds like *Byssochlamys fulva*, spore-forming bacilli as *Clostridium pasteurianum* and *Paenibacillus macerans-polymyxa* group, and certain non spore-forming bacteria (*Lactobacillus* spp.). This flora was known to be eliminated by pasteurization.

Bacillus coagulans, also designated then as *Bacillus thermoacidurans* (11–13), which spoiled processed tomato concentrates and juices, was already well-known as an acidophilic spore former (14).

In the 1980s, the fruit and concentrated juice industry encountered a new significant problem: customers began complaining about spoiled juices that were not over their expiry date. The most prevalent complaints were about an unusual flavor and even a loss of color. Given that no gas was produced, it was first presumed that it was due to chemical contamination, but it was subsequently established that it was due to microbial growth (15). Only spore formers could withstand pasteurization temperatures, and they are required to be acidophilic to thrive in acid juices. After the causative agent of apple juice spoilage was isolated and identified as a novel form of spoilage bacterium, it was named *Bacillus acidoterrestris* (16,17), later reclassified as *Alicyclobacillus acidoterrestris*, within a new genus *Alicyclobacillus*.

It was then concluded that thermo-acidophilic bacteria like *A. acidoterrestris* (and *B. coagulans*) could cause spoilage of heat-processed acidic foods because they form spores with very high heat resistance and can grow at low pH. *B.*

coagulans was since then commonly chosen as a target microorganism for the design of pasteurization and sterilization processes for tomato products, considering the pH and natural tomato soluble solids (NTSS) of the tomato paste (pH below 4.5 and NTSS higher than 24%). As late as 1998, the microorganisms of concern in tomato puree and tomato paste were *Lactobacilli* spp, *B. coagulans*, and *Clostridium pasteurianum* because of spoilage potential, and *C. botulinum* because of pathogenicity (18).

Sources of microbiological contamination in tomato-based products are varied, but being most of the microorganisms soil-borne, diseased and damaged raw material, as well as soil residues, are the main origin of contamination of the production process and final product (19,20).

Microorganisms of concern on tomato based products

Bacillus coagulans: Facultative anaerobic, thermophilic, soil-borne, spore-forming bacterium that is acid-tolerant and thrives well in foods at pH 4.0 to 4.5 at room temperature (21). This is the organism most commonly isolated from spoiled canned vegetables acidified to pH from 4.0 to 4.5 and has been identified as the main source of commercially significant deterioration in thermally processed tomato products (22). It causes a type of deterioration known as “flat sour” in tomato-based products. Although *B. coagulans* is a non-pathogenic microorganism, it may pose a food safety risk due to its potential to raise the pH of acidic foods processed with minimal treatment to a level that allows the germination of surviving *Clostridium botulinum* spores (23,24). Machinery mold (*Geotrichum candidum*) may raise the pH of tomato juice in thin layers to a range optimum for sporulation of *B. coagulans* (25).

Alicyclobacillus acidoterrestris: Obligate aerobe, acid-tolerant, heat resistant, soil-borne, spore-forming, spoilage bacterium. It thrives in temperatures ranging from 26 to 60°C and pH levels ranging from 2.0 to 6.0. Pasteurization methods for juice and beverage products can kill *A. acidoterrestris* spores, but the heat shock provided during the treatment can cause them to germinate. The high variability of this species' strains is an important issue in this case. Heat resistance in spores varies greatly and is dependent on a variety of factors (the strain, the pH, and kind of medium, etc.). Tomato juice and puree damaged by *Alicyclobacillus* spp. have been reported in recent years (26), but spoiling instances in tomato concentrates are not common, because its growth is inhibited by high values of NTSS (15,27) and requires relatively high temperatures (above 37°C) to thrive (28).

Bacillus licheniformis* and *Bacillus subtilis: Obligate aerobe, soil-borne, spore-forming bacteria, able to tolerate extreme environmental conditions. *B. subtilis* spores could germinate and outgrow in tomato juice (pH 4.4) in 4 days at 35°C with inoculum levels as low as 1 spore per ml. However *B. licheniformis* spores could only germinate and outgrow at 10⁴ spores per ml or more. When cultivated aerobically, both *Bacillus* species may elevate the pH of tomato juice to over 4.8 (28).

Clostridium pasteurianum: Obligate anaerobe, acid-tolerant, heat-resistant, soil-borne, spore-forming spoilage bacterium. *C. pasteurianum* spores are abundant in soil. It produces butyric acid, which has a distinct odor and flavor that is highly detectable and disliked by consumers. *C. pasteurianum* spores show higher heat-resistance than other butyric clostridia (29).

Paenibacillus macerans* and *Paenibacillus polymyxa: Facultative anaerobe, acid-tolerant, heat resistant, soil-borne and spore-forming bacteria. Since 1943, there have been various outbreaks of canned food deterioration in which *P. macerans*, *P. polymyxa*, or a combination of these two species has been identified as the source of the spoilage.. The heat resistance of the spores of either species is not particularly high, but of about the same magnitude as that shown for the spores of *Clostridium pasteurianum* (30). *P. macerans* produces a significant amount of histamines which may cause allergies in some individuals, if ingested (31). Although considered non-pathogenic, some species, along with food spoilage, may cause opportunistic infections in humans (32).

***Lactobacillus* spp. (LAB)**. Aerotolerant anaerobes and mesophile microorganisms which have been shown to cause gas formation in tomato-based products (33,34). *Lactobacillus paracasei*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, and *Lactobacillus fructivorans* are the most common isolates from tomato-based spoiled products (35,36). LAB are not generally considered to be heat resistant. *L. fructivorans* has been reported to be more heat resistant than other LAB (27,37).

Saccharomyces cerevisiae. A common soil-borne yeast that is commercially significant in the food and beverage industries, but with an important role as well in food spoilage. The heat resistance of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was reported by Shearer, 2002 (38).

Heat-resistant molds (HRM). These soil-borne fungi include *Neosartorya fischeri*, *Byssochlamys fulva*, *Byssochlamys nivea*, *Talaromyces flavus*, and *Eupenicillium brefeldianum* (39). HRM are basically soil-borne fungi, and fruits that develop in contact with soil are more prone to

contamination. They are often referred to as ascomycetes and their spores are known as ascospores. There are clear indications that ascospores of HRM exhibit constitutive dormancy and need a robust physical signal, as heat, for breaking of dormancy. Dormancy is a kind of hypometabolism that involves any time of rest or reversible disruption of phenotypic development (40). Some HRM may constitute a health danger due to their capacity to create mycotoxins, as well

as altering the quality of food due to visible mycelia and the development of pectinolytic enzymes. *Byssochlamys* sp. produces patulin and byssochlamic acid, and *Neosartorya* sp. produces fumitoxins, fumitremorgins, and verruculogen (39,41). Heat resistance of HRM has been documented, and *D* values were reported for the most relevant of it (42), and specifically in tomato products (43).

TABLE 1– *D* and *z*-values of common spoilage microorganisms found in processed tomato products

Microorganism	T. (°C)	<i>D</i> (min)	<i>z</i> (°C)	Source
<i>B. coagulans</i>	105	1.15	9.20	(44)
<i>A. acidoterrestris</i>	95	5.30	12.9	(45)
<i>C. pasteurianum</i>	95	3.40	9.50	(46)
<i>P. macerans</i>	100	0.50	8.89	(47)
<i>P. polymyxa</i>	100	0.50	8.89	(47)
<i>L. fructivorans</i>	65	1.20	10.00	(35)
<i>L. plantarum</i>	63	0.22	5.59	(48)
<i>L. paracasei</i>	60	0.02	6.49	(49)
<i>N. fischeri</i>	90	6.60	6.63	(43)
<i>B. fulva</i>	90	8.10	6.77	(43)
<i>B. nivea</i>	90	1.50	2.32	(43)
<i>T. flavus</i>	90	6.20	6.40	(50)
<i>E. brefeldianum</i>	60	0.24	3.70	(38)
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	63	1.50	5.20	(38)
<i>G. candidum</i>	55	1.28	4.4	(51)
<i>B. licheniformis</i>	100	2.00	14.90	(52)
<i>B. subtilis</i>	89	1.00	11.90	(53)

D and *z*-values for the microorganisms were selected from a pH range of 4.0 to 4.5, where available. The "Lemgo *D* and *z*-values Database for Food", from the Institute for Food Technology, is a credible source of the parameters needed to develop or validate a pasteurization or sterilization process.

Pathogens of concern in raw tomatoes

Pathogen contamination poses a problem for the fresh produce sector and authorities (54). Some of the pathogens of concern are *Salmonella*

spp. (55), *Shigella* spp., *Campylobacter* spp., *Escherichia coli* O157:H7, *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Fresh tomatoes have long been thought to be

one of the most common sources of produce-borne *L. monocytogenes* outbreaks (56), and there has been also some concern regarding the likelihood of *Bacillus cereus*-like organisms contaminating fresh vegetables. It was speculated that findings of such contamination could be the effect of spraying crops with some biologic insecticides. According to one study, residues of *B. thuringiensis*-based insecticides can be observed on fresh fruits and vegetables and are potentially enterotoxigenic (57,58).

Metabiotic association of *Clostridia* and mold has been demonstrated previously, and *Clostridium sporogenes* and *C. botulinum* can grow, and toxin may be produced by *C. botulinum*, in a metabiotic relationship with fungi in fresh tomatoes (59).

In order to comply with U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) requirements, high-acid and acidified foods with a pH of 4.6 or less must be processed to attain a 5-log reduction in bacterial pathogens (60).

Thermal treatment of aseptically processed tomato paste

The tomato processing industry relies on sterilizing equipments designed for handling products with high consistency — gross viscosity, usually measured with a Bostwick consistometer (61) — and high viscosity values (up to 10 Pa·s) (62), meant for subsequent aseptic filling, where the product is subject to a thermal cycle by means of an indirect heat exchanger of concentric pipes.

The concentric pipe heater is designed to bring the product temperature up to the pre-fixed value by using superheated water. The product circulates inside the central annular space while superheated water circulates in both internal and

external jackets, ensuring effective heat exchange. Any under-processed product is diverted back to the feed tank via a three-way control valve (flow diversion valve) governed by the control system.

The aseptic tubular holder, insulated with rock wool and aluminum sleeves, allows the product exiting the heating section to be held for the holding time resultant from the flow rate at the moment, at the predetermined sterilizing temperature.

The concentric pipe cooler reduces the temperature of the product to 38–42°C. Cooling is accomplished by the indirect circulation of water at a temperature of 14–18°C. The cooler is also made up of a series of concentric pipes, with steam barriers to prevent recontamination in this section.

The aseptic system consists of a heating section, a holding section, a cooling section, and a filling unit. The system runs continuously, processing, in some models, up to 1.8×10^4 kg of tomato paste every hour; it is kept under sterile conditions. A barrier breach in the cooling and filling sections creates the major problem of large volumes of product being packed under non-aseptic conditions and possibly contaminated with viable microorganisms that may develop and spoil the product later during storage and distribution. In the microbiological routine checks used by in-factory laboratories, such recontamination may be discovered only after 36–72 hours (*e.g.* incubation of samples with enriched broth, *Lactobacilli* MRS agar plates, Glucose Chloramphenicol agar plates, etc.).

Production of aseptically processed tomato paste

Fresh tomatoes are inspected for their

transformation suitability, discharged into a channel, and delivered to the roller conveyor, which feeds the distribution flume, after being rinsed using a potable water spraying system, and where soaking takes place. This flume feeds the sorting line. An additional rinsing with potable water is provided by means of spray nozzles. Green, rotten, and damaged tomatoes, as well as all extraneous items, are removed.

The rinsing operations, as well as the soaking period, are essential for the removal of dirt or any material that is not inherent to the fruit. The main source of flat-sour bacteria spores that spoil tomato-based products is field dirt (63). Pesticide residues, microorganisms, sand, fungi, rodent droppings, and *Drosophila* eggs and larvae are just some types of dirt that may be found on tomatoes arriving from the fields.

The ready-to-process tomatoes are chopped and enter the "break" stage, to be heated to either 65–70°C for cold-break processing or to 85–90°C for hot-break processing (64). The chopped tomatoes are conveyed to an extraction unit, usually comprised of a pulper and a refiner. The resulting refined juice is collected in a buffer tank that continuously feeds the multi-effect evaporator.

The most common process for concentrating tomato juice is continuous evaporation under a vacuum. In these conditions, evaporation takes place at a lower temperature than if the juice is boiled at atmospheric pressure. As a result, the paste retains the bulk of the fresh tomato's flavor and color.

The juice inside the multi-effect evaporator flows through different evaporation chambers (or effects) where the concentration level will

gradually increase until the required NTSS value is attained in the final effect. The tomato concentrate is then delivered to the aseptic system buffer tank. From here, it is pumped at high pressure into the aseptic heat exchanger. The actual flow rate in the holding section, which can be determined from the filling rate, and defines the residence time in the holding section, sets the sterilizing temperature.

The sterilization temperatures are calculated for the different filling rates and product characteristics, particularly concentration. It is assumed that the thermal process is only delivered throughout the holding section, and eventual further lethal doses delivered during the heating and cooling phases are usually discarded, because of the variable rates of heat exchange in those stages.

The sterilized tomato concentrate is cooled down to about 38–42°C before being piped into the filling heads. The final temperature value is directly proportional to the filling rate due to the higher holding outlet temperature and shorter residence time in the cooling section of the heat exchanger.

Nowadays, aseptic fillers use steam as the sterilizing agent for both the filling chamber and the aseptic bag fitment, decreasing the risk of microbial recontamination and/or product contamination with chemical disinfectants. The very high level of process automation and control makes it a highly effective and reliable aseptic method for bulk packaging of tomato concentrate. Most of the steps are managed by a programmable logic controller (PLC), like cap pre-sterilization, removal of the cap, filling, and re-capping, as well as the filling chamber auto-sterilization. Sterile filling the aseptic bag is the

final stage of the process.

Aseptic bags used in bag-in-box or bag-in-drum packaging are mainly of the bulk type, having a multi-layered structure consisting of an exterior barrier laminate and an interior bag in contact with the product. All bags are pre-sterilized with gamma irradiation and delivered flat.

There are several specifications for aseptic bags, with different barrier performances, which can affect the shelf-life duration of the product as well as the loss of quality during storage. Metalized polyester (MET-PET) is the standard barrier for aseptic bags and acts as an oxygen-water barrier and blocks out UV rays.

Sources of microbiological spoilage of tomatoes and tomato-based products

The first significant entry point for soil-borne spore-forming organisms into the production process is soil-contaminated tomatoes. If soil-contaminated fruit is introduced into the process, these microorganisms can contaminate the entire production line. As previously indicated, the rinse activities, as well as the soaking period with potable water, are decisive for the removal of soil residues and other contaminants.

It is necessary to limit the percentage damaged and diseased tomatoe, showing evidence of fungal infection or other diseases, accepted at the factory. Tomatoes have a protective epidermis on the outside and a diverse community of microorganisms that colonize the fruit's outermost surface acting as a competitive barrier against spoiling microbes. Internalization, colonization, and lesion formation occur more frequently and rapidly in plant tissue that has been damaged or is otherwise vulnerable. External damage such as bruises, cracks, scars, punctures, worm injuries, and sunburn provide

breeding grounds for spoilage bacteria. This increases the risk of pathogens and spoiling microorganisms making their way into the processing line (20).

Tomatoes may be damaged as a result of mechanical harvesting and bulk transportation. Cracking is the most common post-harvest mechanical damage. As a response, procedures must be put in place to minimize the likelihood of such a scenario, such as defining clear restrictions on the amount and height (1.0–1.5 m) of the load, to avoid, for example, the crushing of the lower layers of tomatoes.

Given the ambient temperatures in the Mediterranean region during tomato season, with an average maximum temperature of 30°C in August, the delay between harvesting and processing is also an important factor in microbial proliferation and growth. If the delay in processing persists for 12 hours or more, spoiling by fungi, oomycetes, and bacteria is likely to increase, especially in the more damaged and even crushed tomatoes in the bottom layers of the load.

Thermo-acidophilic bacteria were found in several processing facility samples, including water from fruit washing, water from flume conveyance, and condensate water from evaporators, in certain documented cases (65). Because tomatoes are frequently unloaded by reusing water from these sources, there may be a concentration of microbes present in the water. Water reuse poses a significant risk, and it is fundamental to give special attention to this type of water source, as well as to the removal of soil accumulation in discharge channels.

Spore-forming bacteria are also able to persist in the processing line by forming biofilms that are

resistant to higienization, and the headspace level of storage tanks or containers, as well as tomato juice flow in non-aseptic pipes, valves and bends, may have an impact on microbial growth (66). Biofilms serve as a reservoir for microbiological contamination of non-sterilized products, thereby increasing the microbial load. Additionally, mold colonization of the biofilm can lead to the formation of mycotoxins. Biofouling in heat exchangers can reduce the efficiency of thermal processes to a point where it becomes a problem (67).

Finally, the facultative-mesophilic nature of some of the spoilage bacteria, such as *B. coagulans*, requires additional precautions during storage, so that a temperature of 30°C is not consistently exceeded (68).

Quality parameters affected by thermal treatment

Tomato paste is described as concentrated tomato juice or pulp, free of skin and seeds, and with at least 24% natural tomato soluble solids (18). The natural tomato soluble solids (NTSS) value is equal to Brix.

Tomato paste is not typically meant for direct consumption, rather it is used as a raw material in various tomato-based products such as ketchups, dehydrated soups and sauces as well as the basis for reconstituted tomato juice and tomato pulp.

This implies that using low quality tomato paste in such tomato-based foods will have a negative impact on the final quality of said products which also are exposed to additional thermal treatments, including pasteurization processes, during its own production.

Considering the above constraint, the main perceived quality parameters of tomato paste are color, titratable acidity (impacting the overall

flavor through the sugar/acid ratio), pH, and consistency, usually evaluated from its Bostwick measurement (69). One of the most significant factors in the commercial quality of tomato products is indeed color, which is the first feature in consumer perception of foods.

Carotenoids are responsible for the tomato paste color; lycopene makes up around 83% of the overall pigment while beta-carotene makes up roughly 3 to 7% (18). Because color determines customer acceptance, it is a significant perceived quality feature in processed tomato concentrate. Tomato paste is subjected to significant thermal treatment during the production process. Under such conditions, lycopene degrades via isomerization and oxidation. At 50°C, lycopene molecules undergo isomerization; at 100°C, degradation is the predominant process (70). Isomerization and degradation of lycopene may reduce up to 17% of its initial value during the thermal treatment (71).

Color, organoleptic characteristics, and other food characteristics, are also affected by non-enzymatic browning reactions or Maillard reactions. Several parameters influence the rate, intensity, and progress of these reactions, including temperature-time combinations, pH, and water activity (72). At more severe heat treatments, the rate of synthesis of Maillard reaction products, such as hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) and furosine, increases (73). Maillard reaction products may be harmful to human health (74) and are an indication of over-heating and/or storage at elevated temperature. Furan, another significant contaminant, is formed as a result of the ascorbic acid, polyunsaturated fatty acid and Maillard reaction pathways. HMF may also be formed by sugar dehydration in acidic

conditions during the heat treatment (75).

Although increasing the process temperature causes non-enzymatic browning reactions to occur, the heated product may show no changes in redness due to the suppressing effect of lycopene (76). Non-enzymatic browning has been considered as one of the major causes of quality and color loss during the processing and storage of tomato products (76). Besides browning, protein solubility reduction, bitter flavor development, and reduced nutritional availability of specific amino acids are all common results of the Maillard reaction.

Titratable total acidity (TA) in tomato paste is usually expressed as the percentage in natural tomato soluble solids of citric acid monohydrate. The higher total acidity in tomato pulp heated at 65–70°C for cold-reak processing at the break step can be linked to the activation of pectolytic enzymes such as pectin-methylesterase (PME) and polygalacturonase (PG). These enzymes cause the formation of pectic, oligouronic, and galacturonic acids from pectic materials which contributes towards the product's higher acidity and lower pH.

The pH value is critical and it should be kept below 4.5 for the reason stated earlier regarding *C. botulinum*. Furthermore, the lower the pH, the lower the possibility of spoilage by thermophilic organisms: the heat resilience of bacterial spores is, in some cases, considerably reduced at lower values of pH for the same temperature (77,78). As a consequence, higher pH values are associated with longer sterilization times. Thermal treatment affects pH in the same way that it affects TA, even though the relationship between TA and pH is not a simple inverse relationship, because the phosphorus in tomato acts as a buffer, regulating

the pH (77).

Another quality factor to consider when determining the overall quality of many tomato products is the viscosity of the paste. Tomato paste comprises both water-soluble and non water-soluble elements. The amount of pectin, total soluble solids, and size distributions of insoluble constituents all play a role in the consistency and viscosity of tomato paste.

The hot-break process uses a higher temperature to inhibit pectolytic enzymes, resulting in a product with a high pectin content and consistency. Conversely, during the cold-reak process, tomatoes are only heated to around 65°C, as previously stated. At this temperature, pectolytic enzymes are not inactivated, resulting in a product with substantially reduced pectin content and, consequently, lower consistency.

Understanding the rheological characteristics of this type of vegetable concentrates is imperative (79). Given the importance of such characterization, for example, in the design of heat-exchangers and establishing the corresponding operational parameters and constraints, it is necessary to accurately assess the rheological parameters of food fluids. Every thermal process design and optimization must take such parameters into account.

Tomato products show significant non-Newtonian effects, such as yield stress, shear thinning behaviour, and shear history dependence. Generally, tomato paste is classified as a pseudoplastic fluid with yield stress. The Bingham model was found to be the best fit for the flow curves of tomato paste by several sources (61,62,80,81).

Two rheological parameters must be considered

to characterize the food fluid type and its flow regime: the flow behaviour index n and the consistency coefficient K . The flow behaviour index shows the degree to which the fluid exhibits non-Newtonian features. The consistency coefficient increases as the fluid becomes more viscous.

Dak (82) observed that the flow behaviour index n of tomato paste is less than the unity, confirming the pseudoplastic, non-Newtonian, nature of tomato concentrate.

The flow behaviour index n is weakly affected by temperature but changes with concentration (82). This parameter will affect the calculation of residence time, hence it must be considered. The consistency coefficient K increases with concentration and decreases with temperature.

The Reynolds number N_{Re} , which is calculated from the characteristic length of the pipes, the density, the flow velocity, and the dynamic and kinematic viscosity values of the food fluid, is another important parameter in any food fluid flow study, and is used to determine the flow regime in the heat-exchanger pipes. This is important because fluid elements in pipes have a range of different velocities and, consequently, real flow behaviour has to be taken into account. The temperature that should be applied cannot be based solely on average velocity because the elements close to the center will be ineffectively sterilized, while those near the periphery will be overheated (83).

It is beyond the scope of this study to go into great detail about these parameters but they were considered in all calculations that will be presented later, and values for rheological parameters of tomato paste, while not always consistent across sources, are reasonably well

established (61,80,82,84).

The influence of temperature at each stage of concentrated tomato processing allows pinpointing sterilization as a stage in the process that may be responsible for relevant color losses (85). Most of the other quality parameters that are influenced by thermal treatments during processing are usually affected to an acceptable or even desired level (*e.g.* consistency). The documented reduction of color parameters confirmed that the excessive heat treatment can reduce the red color of tomato paste (86). "Out-of-spec" or substandard color in tomato products is a serious problem that jeopardizes their commercial viability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is based on the real-time operation of an heat exchanger designed for processing products with high consistency and viscosity values, manufactured by the CFT Group, based in Italy. The Olimpic TC X/AC model has a maximum mass flow rate of $1.8 \times 10^4 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ and can process products with dynamic viscosities up to $1 \times 10^4 \text{ mPa} \cdot \text{s}$ (87), therefore adequate for the sterilization and cooling of cold-reak double and triple-concentrate, as well as hot-break double concentrate.

The holding section of this equipment has a volume V of $5.95 \times 10^{-1} \text{ m}^3$. When processing double concentrated tomato, with an average concentration of 29% NTSS, and a relative density ρ of $1.137 \times 10^3 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$, this equals to a mass of 678.3 kg.

The sterilization temperature T is going to be calculated for a operational situation that can simply be described as filling double concentrated cold-reak tomato paste, with an average

concentration **C** of 29% NTSS and a Bostwick value of 7.0 cm, packed in aseptic bags in drums, each with an average net weight of 239 kg net, at a rate of 42 drums per hour. This equals to a mass flow rate (**W**) of 10,038 Kg·h⁻¹ (a volumetric flow rate **Q** of 2.45×10⁻³ m³·s⁻¹).

Some consideration must be given to the flow regime in the holding section, because some corrections may be necessary in the estimation of the residence time. For that purpose, some

rheological parameters must be calculated for the food fluid in this study and are presented in Table 2.

Reaching a turbulent flow regime with fluids having a significant yield stress is difficult. Laminar flow can be expected when **N_{Re,B}** is lower than the critical Bingham Reynolds number, which in this case is 11.23 (84). The calculated Reynolds number indicates a laminar flow regime in the tubular holding section.

TABLE 2– Operational and rheological parameters for the described filling conditions.

Brix	Bostwick	Dynamic viscosity μ ^(a)	Relative density ρ ^(b)	Flow behaviour index n ^(c)	Consistency coeff. K ^(d)	Mean velocity u_{mean} ^(e)	Max. velocity u_{max} ^(f)	$\frac{u_{mean}}{u_{max}}$	Bingham Reynolds number $N_{Re,B}$ ^(g)
%	cm	Pa·s	kg·m ⁻³		Pa·s ⁿ	m·s ⁻¹	m·s ⁻¹		
29.0	7.0	4.5	1.137×10 ³	0.33	1.24	2.67×10 ⁻¹	4.14×10 ⁻¹	6.66×10 ⁻¹	7.29

(a) Dynamic viscosity at 32°C (88). Decreases with increase in temperature (89).

(b) Relative density at 25°C (90). Decreases with increase in temperature (91).

(c) Calculated from Fito (79). Similar to the one indicated by Kubo (80), and Rao (61).

(d) Calculated from Alamprese (92), for a temperature between 105 and 115 °C.

(e) Calculated from the volumetric flow **Q** and the cross-sectional area **A** (holding section).

(f) Maximum velocity is calculated from equation (1): $u_{max} = (3 \times n + 1)/(n + 1) \times u_{mean}$

(g) Calculated from Steffe (93).

Based on the equipment's characteristics and the operational and rheological parameters, it is also needed to calculate the mean holding time τ_{hold} , from equation (2): V/Q . In this instance, the calculated τ_{hold} is 235 s. A correction is necessary, due to the laminar regime of the flow, and from the u_{mean}/u_{max} ratio, the τ_{hold} to be considered is 235/1.5 = 157 s, i.e. 2.61 min.

It is now possible to calculate the temperature to be attained in the sterilizer holding section, considering the D and z-values of the microorganism of reference, and the target log-reduction. The

sterilization temperature to be applied is based on spoilage organisms rather than food pathogens, and a food safety approach will be followed regarding the latter. A 6-log reduction (6D) in microbiological load is commonly used when recommending methods for acidified and high-acid foods (47).

The average bioburden in harvested tomatoes varies greatly and is mostly dependent on the soil contamination, irrigation water quality, and fruit health: the freshness and integrity of tomato being processed is very important. The total aerobic count may be as high as 9×10⁵ CFU/g, and

the coliform count may reach 7×10^6 CFU/g. According to one study, fourteen bacteria genera were isolated and identified in fresh tomato samples (94). Several of the detected bacterial species are foodborne pathogens that can constitute public health risks, thus appropriate handling and heat processing before packing is required. Furthermore, most of the spoilage microorganisms are soil-borne.

Regarding color, a preliminary study was carried on during the 2021 crop, comparing the color values from tomato paste sterilized at different temperatures: 98 samples of double concentrated tomato paste, cold-reak type, were collected after filling, and the color values as well as the holding outlet temperatures were registered for each sample.

A previous study, during the 2020 season, evaluated the color values of tomato paste at the evaporator's outlet (final effect). The temperature at the evaporator's final effect ranges from 70 to 80°C. Forty-five samples of 36/38% tomato paste were tested. It was also possible to compare the results of 9 of those samples with the color values after sterilization and cooling.

The color of tomato paste was measured using a ColorFlex® EZ Tomato Spectrophotometer, from Hunterlab, and results were expressed in Hunter **L a b** scale. This scale is known to provide better differentiation between minor color changes in the darker area of the color space, as well as good differentiation for saturated colors, as is the case with tomato-based products (95). The measurement procedure is based on the "Method for the color measurement of unsalted tomato paste / concentrate (modified COST90bis procedure)", first published in the Annex A of the report EUR 13392 from the Community Bureau of Reference.

Tomato Paste Scores were calculated from USDA formula (96):

$$-81.5182 + 1.609 \times a + 15.390 \times b - 0.591 \times b^2$$

This score ignores the **L** value. The author thought it would be useful to assess the eventual influence of the thermal treatment on this parameter. A numerical score (hence referred to as the CPScore) was developed and used to measure the impact on all color parameters, **L**, **a**, and **b**:

$$CPScore = \frac{B-Y+R}{100} \quad \text{equation (2)}$$

where:

$$B = 2 \times L^3 \times x \quad \text{equation (3)}$$

$$Y = 2 \times b^3 \quad \text{equation (4)}$$

$$R = a^3 \times x \quad \text{equation (5)}$$

and x is the CIE chromaticity index:

$$x = \frac{a+1.75 \times L}{5.645 \times L + a - 3.012 \times b} \quad \text{equation (6)}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the 2021 tomato season, the CPScore was calculated from 1,020 color data from an aseptic filling line. The preliminary findings suggest a strong correlation with the Hunter **a** value (Figure 1), but a moderate to poor correlation with the **b** and **L** values (Figures 2 and 3). To determine its validity and usefulness for evaluating the influence of the sterilizing procedure on tomato paste color characteristics, an extended research, anticipated for the 2022 season, is required.

The colour values of unsterilized product, collected during the 2020 season, show the same trends and it is evident that the CPScore is higher in the pre-sterilization product (Figures 4, 5 and 6, and table 3).

Figure 1– Hunter a x CPScore

Figure 2– Hunter b x CPScore

Figure 3– Hunter L x CPScore

**Figure 4– Hunter a x CPScore
(unsterilized product)**

**Figure 5– Hunter b x CPScore
(unsterilized product)**

**Figure 6– Hunter L x CPScore
(unsterilized product)**

TABLE 3— Comparison of color values pre/post-sterilization in 36/38% tomato paste

Sample	L _{pre}	L _{pos}	a _{pre}	a _{pos}	b _{pre}	b _{pos}	CPScore _{pre}	CPScore _{pos}
2	25.36	23.52	33.08	32.59	14.84	14.28	340	307
6	25.37	23.67	33.98	32.96	15.16	14.58	359	316
8	25.50	23.37	33.27	31.93	15.07	14.27	345	292
10	26.04	23.36	33.70	32.26	15.45	14.39	361	298
11	25.38	23.67	33.67	32.30	15.21	14.51	352	302
16	25.37	22.79	34.01	32.16	15.20	14.04	359	291
17	26.35	23.00	33.75	32.47	15.28	14.07	368	299
19	23.97	23.61	33.15	31.96	15.04	14.25	322	295
22	25.58	23.32	33.85	32.82	15.31	14.48	358	309

pre: samples collected at the evaporator's final effect;

pos: samples collected at the filling line, after sterilization and cooling.

TABLE 4 – Calculated sterilization temperatures **T** for 7, 6 and 5-log reductions.

Microorganism		T _{ref} (°C)	D min	z (°C)	Source	T (7D)	F _T		F _T	
C. botulinum	(a)	100	17.80	12.10	(10)	120.4	124.6	T (5D)	118.6	89.0
<i>B. licheniformis</i>		100	2.00	14.90	(52)	110.9	14.0	T (6D)	109.9	12.0
<i>A. acidoterrestris</i>		95	5.30	12.90	(45)	109.9	37.1	T (6D)	109.1	31.8
<i>B. coagulans</i>		105	1.15	9.20	(44)	109.6	8.1	T (6D)	108.9	6.9
<i>C. pasteurianum</i>		95	3.40	9.50	(46)	104.2	23.8	T (6D)	103.5	20.4
B. cereus	(a)	90	5.60	10.00	(58)	101.8	39.2	T (5D)	100.4	28.0
<i>P. macerans</i>		100	0.50	8.89	(47)	101.2	3.5	T (6D)	100.6	3.0
<i>P. polymyxa</i>		100	0.50	8.89	(47)	101.2	3.5	T (6D)	100.6	3.0
<i>B. fulva</i>		90	8.10	6.77	(43)	99.1	56.7	T (6D)	98.6	48.6
<i>N. fischeri</i>		90	6.60	6.63	(43)	98.3	46.2	T (6D)	97.9	39.6
<i>T. flavus</i>		90	6.20	6.40	(43)	97.9	43.4	T (6D)	97.4	37.2
C. perfringens	(a)	95	0.50	10.00	(46)	96.3	3.5	T (5D)	94.9	2.5
<i>B. subtilis</i>		89	1.00	11.90	(53)	94.2	7.0	T (6D)	93.4	6.0
<i>B. nivea</i>		90	1.50	2.32	(43)	91.5	10.5	T (6D)	91.3	9.0
Shigella spp	(a)	65	3.00	10.00	(97)	74.1	21.0	T (6D)	73.4	18.0
Campylobacter spp	(a)	72	0.50	7.00	(98)	72.9	3.5	T (5D)	71.9	2.5
E. coli O157:H7	(a)	71	0.48	8.50	(98)	72.1	3.4	T (6D)	71.5	2.9
L. monocytogenes	(a)	71	0.48	8.50	(98)	72.1	3.4	T (5D)	70.8	2.4
S. enterica	(a)	71	0.48	8.50	(98)	72.1	3.4	T (5D)	70.8	2.4
<i>L. fructivorans</i>		65	1.20	10.00	(35)	70.1	8.4	T (6D)	69.5	7.2
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>		63	1.50	5.20	(38)	66.2	10.5	T (5D)	65.4	7.5
<i>L. plantarum</i>		63	0.22	5.59	(48)	61.8	1.6	T (6D)	61.4	1.3
<i>E. brefeldianum</i>		60	0.24	3.70	(38)	59.3	1.7	T (6D)	59.1	1.4
<i>G. candidum</i>		55	1.28	4.4	(51)	57.5	9	T (6D)	57.2	7.7
<i>L. paracasei</i>		60	0.02	6.49	(49)	51.8	0.1	T (6D)	51.4	0.1

(a) As required by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration, a minimum 5-log reduction was considered (60).

The sterilization temperatures presented in Table 4 were calculated for the microorganisms detailed earlier in **Microorganisms of Concern** and **Pathogens of Concern**.

It is accepted that a successful sterilization kills microorganisms or destroys infectious proteins, viruses etc., and that the sterilization process enables the sterilization probability to be increased almost at will, but zero microbes per

given unit cannot be reached. Furthermore, given the potential for post-sterilization contamination in aseptic processing, we cannot approach the absolute negative that is sterility.

The 7-log reduction presented as the target for the inactivation of the thermo-acidophilic bacteria in tomato paste may be considered a worst-case scenario. Being soil-borne bacteria, it is practically impossible to estimate the bioburden of the fresh

tomato processed in an ongoing production flow. The concentration of coliform bacteria on the surfaces of tomatoes grown in polluted soil revealed no anomalous overall contamination, according to one study (99). Even so, one single delivery of sub-standard raw tomato may increase the juice's initial bioburden, due to the mixing of several loads prior to processing.

As expected from the sources reviewed, the most temperature-demanding microorganisms are the heat-resistant, spore-formers bacteria *C. botulinum*, *B. licheniformis*, *A. acidoterrestris*, *B. coagulans*, *C. pasteurianum*, and *B. cereus*.

From those, two are pathogens of concern: *C. botulinum* and *B. cereus*. In what concerns *C. botulinum*, the 7D process for the most resistant spoilage microorganisms will not ensure inactivation of the most heat-resistant type F proteolytic spores (68). Even so, residual spores would be unable to germinate and grow due to the pH value which does not support *C. botulinum* spore germination and growth (6).

When the food safety management system implemented can assure that there is no possibility of growth, a Food Safety Objective based on an absence of *C. botulinum* spores is not the most appropriate criterion. The metric for hazard control (still based on prevention of toxin formation) is the assurance of no growth (100).

Botulinum toxins are easily destroyed by heat, and, in general, the toxins are more stable in acid food. Heating the food to an internal temperature of 85°C for at least 5 minutes will inactivate 10^5 LD₅₀ of botulinum toxin per gram of food to no detectable toxin, in tomato juice with pH 4.1 (101). Considering the lowest **T** value calculated for the spoilage microorganisms (*B. coagulans*, 109.6°C), the equivalent process time would be 1 s (102).

For *B. cereus*, the sterilization temperature required for a 5-log reduction is lower than that required for an equivalent reduction of the most heat-resistant spoilage microorganisms, *B. licheniformis*, *A. acidoterrestris*, and *B. coagulans*. Hence, a sterilization process targeting those spoilage bacteria can inactivate this pathogen. Moreover, a pH lower than 4.3 will not support the growth of *B. cereus*.

Some regulations require that a treatment must be put in place by the industry that results in at least a 5-log reduction of the most resistant microorganism of public health significance that is likely to occur in the food product. In Table 3, it can be observed that for all food pathogens, with the exception of *C. botulinum*, the temperatures required for a 5-log reduction are well below those required for the spoilage bacteria.

From the calculated values, *B. licheniformis* is the most heat-resistant of the remaining spoilage bacteria but some sources documented that a pH of 4.4 is the bacterium's growth limiting factor. Only a small part of the *B. licheniformis* spore population can germinate and develop at a pH as low as 4.4. At this pH level, tomato juice appears to be bactericidal to *B. licheniformis* spores, and more than 10^4 spores per ml are needed to outgrow aerobically (28).

A. acidoterrestris is the second most resistant bacterium considered. Some authors report that if a preliminary spore activation (for instance, 20 minutes at 70°C) is followed by proper inactivation, the decimal reduction time is significantly reduced (65,103). Nowadays, this bacterium is suggested to be considered the target microorganism for pasteurization processes of high-acid, shelf-stable, fruit products by some researchers, noting the absence of target or criterion in pasteurization of

such food products (104).

B. coagulans is frequently isolated from spoiled acidic or acidified foods, particularly tomato products. It has been employed for decades as the target microorganism in the design of thermal processes for the sterilization of tomato products due to its superior thermal resistance compared to saccharolytic and butyric spore producing anaerobes (14,105).

Regarding *C. pasteurianum*, process parameters designed to reduce spoiling caused by *B. coagulans* growth will also prevent spoilage induced by *C. pasteurianum* growth in tomato products (106).

The sterilization temperatures presented in Table 5 were calculated for 1 to 14 log reductions of *B. coagulans*, considering the residence time of 2.61 min. The log-reductions and corresponding temperatures indicated in Table 5 will be henceforth used in the evaluation of the sterilization impact on tomato paste color.

TABLE 5– Holding temperatures for *B. coagulans*

Holding time (min)= 2.61	
Log-reduction	Holding outlet temp. (°C)
1	101.8
2	104.5
3	106.2
4	107.3
5	108.2
6	108.9
7	109.6
8	110.1
9	110.6
10	111.0
11	111.4
12	111.7
13	112.0
14	112.3

Averages of the color results of the 98 samples,

grouped by log-reduction intervals, are presented in Table 6.

TABLE 6– Average **L a b** values, 14 to 7D processes

Log red.	Avg. L	Avg. a	Avg. b	Avg. a/b
14	23.32	31.81	14.15	2.25
13	23.26	31.90	14.10	2.26
12	23.34	31.95	14.07	2.27
11	23.45	31.95	14.10	2.27
10	23.50	32.06	14.12	2.27
9	23.48	32.25	14.12	2.28
8	23.58	32.21	14.13	2.28
7	23.54	32.19	14.11	2.28

The effect of the sterilization temperature, from the 2021 industrial-scale preliminary study is evident, namely in the **L** and **a** color parameters (Figures 4 and 5). The **b** color parameter seems to be not significantly affected (Figure 6). As expected, the **a/b** ratio reflects the decline in the **a** color parameter (Figure 7).

Average color scores by log-reduction level are presented in Table 7.

TABLE 7– Average Scores (14 to 7D processes)

Log red.	Avg. TPS	Avg. CPScore
14	232	290
13	232	291
12	233	293
11	232	294
10	233	297
9	233	300
8	233	301
7	233	300

The severity of the sterilization process does not affect the USDA’s Tomato Paste Score TPS (Figure 8). The CPScore, on the other hand, appears to indicate the color loss caused by this heat treatment (Figure 9).

Figure 4– Hunter L x log-reduction

Figure 5– Hunter a x log-reduction

Figure 6– Hunter b x log-reduction

Figure 7– a/b ratio x log-reduction

Figure 8– Tomato Paste Score x log-reduction

Figure 9– CPScore x log-reduction

Enumeration of thermophilic <i>Clostridia</i>	< LoQ					
Enumeration of mesophilic <i>Clostridia</i>	< LoQ					
Enumeration of total coliforms	< LoQ					
Enumeration of beta-glucuronidase-positive <i>E. coli</i>	< LoQ					
Enumeration of <i>Lactobacillus</i> spp.	< LoQ					
Detection of <i>L. monocytogenes</i> in 25g	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
Detection of <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in 25g	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
Enumeration of <i>S. aureus</i>	< LoQ					

Note: LoQ = 10 CFU/g

In terms of microbiological stability, the results of the microbiological analysis (Table 8) suggested that a 7-log reduction method yields the same results as an 11-log reduction process.

Most mycotoxins are heat-resistant within the range of food-processing temperatures (80–121°C), hence these time-temperature profiles will result in little to no reduction in overall toxin levels.

CONCLUSIONS

It is then possible to assume that thermo-acidophilic, soil-borne bacteria from the families Bacillaceae, genus *Bacillus*, Alicyclobacillaceae, genus *Alicyclobacillus*, and Clostridiaceae, genus *Clostridium*, are the microorganisms of concern in the sterilization of tomato double and triple concentrated. The other spoilage microorganisms such as the *Lactobacilli* and the heat-resistant ascomycetes exhibited lower heat-resistance than the thermo-acidophilic spoilage bacteria.

B. coagulans has been used as the reference microorganism in the sterilization of aseptically processed tomato concentrate. Despite *A. acidoterrestris* having a higher thermal resistance, double and triple-concentrated tomato paste are likely to limit its development due to the high soluble solids content. Limiting factors that may be present in the food matrix are important for the final selection of the target microorganism in the

sterilization of double and triple-concentrated tomato paste: As stated earlier, *B. licheniformis* requires a pH above 4.4 to grow and germinate (28), and *A. acidoterrestris* growth is suppressed by high soluble solids concentrations (15,27). A double-concentrated tomato paste has a NTSS range between 28 and 30%; a triple-concentrated one, between 36 and 38%; pH values are in the interval 4.10 to 4.40, the average for cold-reak tomato paste is 4.30.

The sterilization temperature calculated for a 7-log reduction of *B. coagulans* (109.6°C) is higher than the temperatures required for 5-log reductions of all the relevant pathogens.

This temperature, is, in practical terms, the temperature required for a 6-log reduction of *A. acidoterrestris* (109.1°C) and *B. licheniformis* (109.9°C).

Applying a temperature of 109.6°C for 2.61 minutes will also meet the suggested time-temperature profiles for high acid and acidified products (47).

A low initial bioburden is crucial: good hygiene and manufacturing practices, preventive programs, and production flow optimized for the safety of the product, will maintain the microbial load as low as possible, so that the 6 to 7-log reductions of the thermo-acidophilic spoilage bacteria are adequate.

The quantity of soil particles and the amount of *B. coagulans* spores in the water used to wash tomatoes have a direct link. This bacterium can grow in the washing equipment if cold water is not introduced in adequate quantities, allowing water temperatures to rise above 30°C (107). Controlling the pH in the final product is essential too, and it must be kept consistently below 4.40.

It should be reinforced that temperatures in the growing areas might easily approach 40°C during harvest or raw material delivery. During the season, long lines of lorries can sometimes be observed at the plants waiting to unload. During this period, microbial development causes spoiling. Mold and lactic acid bacteria, in particular, begin to proliferate. As a result, it is essential to process healthy tomatoes as fast as possible. The lengthier the operation, the higher the contamination with molds and other bacteria, and thus their metabolic products like lactic acid or mycotoxins might be found in the product.

Hence, if the sterilization step is a Critical Control Point in a HACCP plan, a minimum 5-log reduction ($F_{105^{\circ}\text{C}}^{9.2} = 5.8 \text{ min}$) should be its critical limit. For instance, the temperature set point of the flow diversion valve should be set to this limit, and the valve operation must be checked at an established frequency.

Another factor to consider is that an aseptic process requires a sterilized product to be placed within a sterilized package, which is then sealed under sterile conditions. Therefore, after sterilization, it is essential to ensure that any risk of recontamination is minimized or eliminated during the cooling and filling processes, as well as during storage and distribution. Not all microorganisms must be eliminated in order for the product to be considered commercially sterile, but

microorganisms that are capable of growing in non-refrigerated storage and distribution conditions must be absent from the tomato paste.

Minimizing the impact of sterilization on the most notable aspects of tomato paste color – brightness and redness, expressed by the *L* and *a* value in color measurement – can be achieved by selecting the lowest possible temperature value and ensuring that product flow variations during production time are reflected in the heat treatment applied. The impact in color was evidenced by two preliminary studies, that will be continued during the 2022 season.

Adopting the lowest sterilizing temperature possible will improve energy efficiency by reducing steam consumption and, as a result, fuel consumption and GHG emissions, reducing environmental impact. To raise the temperature of 1.0 kg of double-concentrated tomato paste by one degree Celsius, 3,500 J of energy is required. Extrapolating for the production of $3.0 \cdot 10^7$ kg of tomato paste every season, a 1°C reduction in the heating section final temperature would result in CO₂ emissions reductions of approximately 6,700 kg if using Natural Gas, or 9,400 kg if using Fuel Oil (108).

All factors considered, the author concludes that establishing a 7-log reduction of *B. coagulans* ($F_{105^{\circ}\text{C}}^{9.2} = 8.1 \text{ min}$) as the sterilization target in the aseptic production of double and triple-concentrated tomato paste will reduce sensory and nutritional quality deterioration while providing an appropriate level of protection.

RESOURCES

To assist in the calculation of all the values needed to establish a reliable sterilization process, the author has created an online calculator, using his spreadsheet, used for the past 20 years to publish "Sterilization Temperature-Time" tables, used in the production of aseptically processed tomato paste at a major tomato processing factory in Portugal.

GRID is an online application that allows the creation of calculator-like documents on top of spreadsheets such as MS-Excel®. [The generated calculator](#) is available for free online (109) and it can assist in the calculating procedure. The reference microbe and intended log-reduction, as well as the dimensions of the holding section, the type of food fluid and its rheological properties, can all be selected. It can also be used for the calculation of the temperature correction to be applied in the case of uninsulated holding pipes.

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